

Innovative Business Models to Foster Transition

Deliverable D6.4

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This project has received funding from the *European Union's Horizon 2020* research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 657998

Document Information

Grant Agreement #: 657998

Project Title: Energy System Transition Through Stakeholder Activation, Education and Skills Development

Project Acronym: ENTRUST

Project Start Date: 01 May 2015

Related work package: WP6: Energy Transitions Pathways

Related task(s): T6.5 Innovative business models to foster transition

Lead Organisation: University College Cork

Submission date: 30 April 2018

Dissemination Level: Public

History

Date	Submitted by	Reviewed by	Version (Notes)
24 April 2018	UCC	All	A

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About the ENTRUST Project

ENTRUST is mapping Europe’s energy system (key actors and their intersections, technologies, markets, policies, innovations) and aims to achieve an in-depth understanding of how human behaviour around energy is shaped by both technological systems and socio-demographic factors (especially gender, age and socio-economic status). New understandings of energy-related practices and an intersectional approach to the socio-demographic factors in energy use will be deployed to enhance stakeholder engagement in Europe’s energy transition.

The role of gender will be illuminated by intersectional analyses of energy-related behaviour and attitudes towards energy technologies, which will assess how multiple identities and social positions combine to shape practices. These analyses will be integrated within a transitions management framework, which takes account of the complex meshing of human values and identities with technological systems. The third key paradigm informing the research is the concept of energy citizenship, with a key goal of ENTRUST being to enable individuals to overcome barriers of gender, age and socio-economic status to become active participants in their own energy transitions.

Central to the project will be an in-depth engagement with five very different communities across Europe that will be invited to be co-designers of their own energy transition. The consortium brings a diverse array of expertise to bear in assisting and reflexively monitoring these communities as they work to transform their energy behaviours, generating innovative transition pathways and business models capable of being replicated elsewhere in Europe.

For more information see <http://www.entrust-h2020.eu>

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1 Introduction

1.1 Background

There are significant societal pressures, regulatory drivers, and economic opportunities in the delivery of low-carbon intensity solutions. This is particularly in the case of the built environment, but increasing also in the transport and other sectors. Yet the roll-out of these low-carbon products and services is insufficient to achieve the level of energy savings and avoidance of greenhouse gas emissions required if international commitments to stabilise atmospheric levels of greenhouse gases are to be met

There are a variety of barriers that inhibit the development of, and take-up of more sustainable business models. Some of these barriers are place-specific, while others are more generally applicable. For example, In the building sector, notwithstanding the demonstrable economic opportunities associated with reducing energy demand and the associated ‘carbon intensity’ of the built environment, the European Commission notes that “Energy efficiency in buildings suffers from underinvestment” (2016, p. 5) and outlines a number of barriers including: competition for capital; lack of trustworthy information, lack of skilled workers; doubts on possible benefits (*ibid.*)

In the energy sector, as reported in an earlier report, ENTRUST deliverable 2.3, Boo, Molinero, *et al.* . (2017)¹ identified a number of barriers, which have inhibited the development and implementation of business models (focusing on the energy system) to foster the energy transition. Table 1 below summarises the types of barriers identified in this work.

Socio-Market	Financial	Regulatory	Innovation
Lack of knowledge, consumer engagement and trust	Lack of affordable financing for renewables and energy efficiency works	Cumbersome regulations (<i>e.g.</i> , restrictive rules discouraging new approaches)	Difficult in moving from idea to implementation
Insufficient standards and reference guides	High upfront costs associated	Lack of policies (policy context lagging technology and business innovation)	Difficult in scaling
Infrastructure dependence	Low return on investment		Not always focus on market needs
Perceived risk in renewables			

Table 1: Barriers for the energy transition (after Boo, Molinero, *et al.* 2017 pp. 18-19)

¹ Boo, E., Molinero, S., Sanvicente, E., de Melo, P., Landini, A., Ota, J., Chichinata, Orsetta, Melchiorre, T., Melia, A., 2017. *Novel business models and main barriers in the EU energy system*. ENTRUST Deliverable 2.3.

Analogues of many of these barriers were also found in subsequent work, ENTRUST deliverable 6.3 in which Morrissey, Axon, *et al.*, (2017)², identified potential barriers to transition innovation pathways. Of particular note were potential issues identified with respect to: infrastructure *e.g.*, continued reliance on traditional energy infrastructure (*ibid.*, p. 54); access to finance (*ibid.*, p. 69); societal barriers including access to health (*ibid.*, p. 23); and education, and gender inequality (*ibid.*, p. 46); weak socio-political structures (*ibid.*, p. 46).

While some of the barriers are structural requiring action by state entities or equivalent, this is not always the case. Many of the barriers inhibiting businesses changing the way in which they do business towards a more sustainable less carbon intensive can be overcome through business model innovation. Casadesu-Masanell & Ricart (2010) describe business models as referring “... to the ‘logic of the firm’ - how it operates and creates value for its stakeholders”. The essence of a business model is in other words the manner by which the enterprise delivers value to customers, entices customers to pay for value, and converts those payments to profit (Teece, 2010). Business model innovation to foster transition therefore requires a consideration of the values desired by customers and a marrying of these customer desires with societal demand (including increasing regulatory drivers) for reduced climate impacts of key goods and services. For example, in ENTRUST deliverable 5.3, Lennon, Dunphy, *et al.*, (2018)³ looked at community-level sustainable approaches to energy management. Seven scenarios were forwarded as examples of how community focused sustainable / renewable energy projects could be realised. This work focused on implementation of goal-orientated energy projects using existing funding mechanisms and leveraging novel cooperation mechanisms to realise community-orientated energy project than fit the locally-specific contexts in which they are situated.

1.2 Aim of the deliverable

The aim of this deliverable is to forward concepts of novel business models which will contribute to the fostering of the energy transition through addressing specific social, market and other barriers. The objective being to facilitate stakeholders (whether suppliers or consumers of energy) to shape and progressively interact with the energy system to effectively deliver a low-carbon system. The examples of (more) sustainable business models forwarded in this report will in particular, but not entirely focus on community-based approaches (complementing the work presented in Lennon, Dunphy *et al.*, 2018) and public-private partnerships as a means of addressing issues such as public acceptance, split incentives, risk sharing, *etc.*

² Morrissey, J., Axon, S., Hillman, J., Perez, S.M., Lennon, B., Dunphy, N.P., 2017. *Innovation Pathways to Transition*. ENTRUST Deliverable 6.3.

³ Lennon, B., Dunphy, N.P., Sanvicente, E., Hillman, J., Morrissey, J.E., 2018. *Energy Management Approaches for Sustainable Communities*. ENTRUST Deliverable 5.3

1.3 Structure of the document

The first section of presents the background to this component of the research project, it outlines objectives and aims, describes the contents and structure of the report and positions it in relation to the related outputs from the ENTRUST project.

The second section gives an overview on the energy transition, it discusses the nature of the of the ongoing transition from a fossil fuel dominated system to a low carbon intensity system. The European dimension of the energy transition is discussed and arguments forwarded the need to develop new ways of doing business to foster transition.

The third section explores concepts relating to value creation, delivery and capture. which are so central to business model design. The business model itself is considered conceptually and the links between business models and innovation discussed.

The fourth section explores project delivery methods – which while often conflated with the concept of business model it is useful to consider the possible types of project configuration at a theoretical level before progressing to business models.

The fifth section details a number of key identified social and/or market barriers to the adoption of sustainable business approaches and forwards business models, which will aim to address such barriers in a manner that will offer the prospective for ready uptake and widespread deployment thus having the potential to contribute to the transformation in the way in which we as a society relate to, value, and consume energy.

1.4 Relationship to other deliverables

As mentioned above a number of previous outputs from the ENTRUST project have dealt with innovation and business models in relation to energy and the energy system. Three reports are of particular relevance, namely: Boo, Molinero, *et al.* (Boo et al., 2017), which identified and characterised novel business models and the main barriers within the EU energy system; Morrissey, Axon, *et al.*, (Morrissey et al., 2017), which examined innovation pathways for the energy transition; and Lennon, Dunphy, *et al.*, (2018), which explored energy management approaches for sustainable communities. This report both builds on, and is informed by, the work presented in these reports to forward business models which will aim to address specific market and social barriers, which work to discourage market moves towards energy transition by disincentivizing adoption of less carbon intensive ways of doing business.

2 Energy transitions

2.1 Background

The concept of ‘transition’ has become increasingly central to futures-oriented thinking (Feola and Nunes, 2014), in recognition that deeply embedded socio-ecological problems urgently require novel approaches combined with long-term orientations. Since the late 1990s a significant body of literature has emerged, highlighting the need for a longer term approach to sustainability (Geels 2002; Kemp 1994; Schot & Geels, 2007). Central to the literature on transitions is the argument that policy shifts to longer-term perspectives and approaches are critical for environmental sustainability (Geels, 2011; Kemp, Rotmans, & Loorbach, 2007). The emerging field is characterised by a wide range of approaches and methodologies, but commonly, transitions towards sustainability are framed from a systems perspective (Farla, Markard, Raven, & Coenen, 2012). Kern (2012) states that within the socio-technical transitions literature, scholars have explored ways through which relatively stable configurations of technologies, infrastructures, social practices, institutions and markets can change to provide societal functions such as energy provision, transport and nutritional supply in a more sustainable way. A comprehensive review of transitions ideas can be found in Geels (2010); Hansen and Coenen (2015) and Lachman (2013).

The Multi-level Perspective (MLP) represents a central socio-technical transitions approach. This heuristic has gained significant traction, largely due to advantages in its scope and general applicability, as discussed by Geels (2011) and Lachman (2013). The MLP is a hybrid theoretical framework bridging science and technology studies and evolutionary economics and draws extensively on institutional analysis as a middle ground spanning these approaches (Coenen, Benneworth, & Truffer, 2012). The MLP distinguishes between three levels of heuristic approach, with analytical concepts that combine as a nested hierarchy to create a socio-technical system (Crabbé, Jacobs, Van Hoof, Bergmans, & Van Acker, 2013). Within the MLP nested hierarchy, transitions come about through interactions between processes at three levels: (a) niche-innovations afford space for new ideas to be tested and developed⁴; (b) changes at the landscape level create pressure on the regime; and (c) destabilisation of the regime creates windows of opportunity for niche innovations to emerge. A central tenet in MLP is the stabilising influence of a socio-technical regime (Coenen et al., 2012). A focus on regimes recognises that organisations and technologies are embedded within wider social and economic systems (Rip & Kemp, 1998). An individual regime is an articulation of a current social paradigm that is itself the sum of current practices, beliefs, methods, technologies, behaviours, routines and rules for societal functions (Rip & Kemp, 1998). (Coenen et al., 2012) refer to Rip and Kemp’s (Rip & Kemp, 1998) description of a socio-technical regime as “the coherent complex of scientific knowledge, engineering practices, production process technologies, product characteristics, skills and procedures, established user

⁴ Niches of innovation offer opportunities to experiment with new practices, technologies and organizational models, with subsequent potential for wider social transformation, should these niche innovations be suitable for wider uptake and diffusion (Geels, 2002; Geels and Schot, 2007; Seyfang and Smith, 2007; Seyfang, 2010).

needs, regulatory requirements, institutions and infrastructures". These factors form a deep and embedded structure which is characteristically difficult to change by niche pressure due to lock-in and stability characteristics (Geels, 2011). Figure 1 describes the three levels of heuristic, analytical concepts which comprise the MLP, including niche innovations, socio-technical regimes and the socio-technical landscape after (Nykvist & Whitmarsh, 2008).

Figure 1: The Multi-Level Perspective (MLP) on Transition (Nykvist and Whitmarsh, 2008; Geels, 2012; Morrissey and Heidkamp, 2017).

Socio-technical regimes only undertake a transition from one stable state to another when there is alignment of external pressures with mature innovations (respectively represented by Landscape and Niche innovations in Figure 1). The alignment of these processes enables the breakthrough of novelties in mainstream markets where they compete with the existing regime (Geels and Schot, 2007). Depending on timing and qualitatively different niche-regime-landscape interactions, transitions can evolve following different types of transition pathways (Schot & Geels, 2007). Niches act as ‘incubation rooms’ or ‘protected spaces’ shielding novelties from the pressures of the mainstream including, for example, the forces of market selection (Schot, 1998; Kemp et al., 1998). Radical innovations break out of the niche-level when ongoing processes at the levels of regime and landscape create a ‘window of opportunity’, which allow these niche innovations to go on to become integral to regimes (Geels and Schot, 2007). Avelino *et al.* (2017) propose a co-evolutionary understanding for social innovation, a framing consistent with an MLP understanding of transformative change. Such social innovation can constitute the development of skills, knowledge and social capital, through interventions coming from multiple levels and focused on different aspects of energy generation, supply and use (i.e. finance and technical implementation) (Hiteva & Sovacool, 2017).

There are significant challenges related to the diffusion of niche innovations, particularly related to the scale of niche innovations within a wider regime, making scale-up challenging and presenting difficulties with replication of conditions for success across wider regime environments (Charnock, 2007; Seyfang and Smith,

2007; Seyfang, 2010). Niche innovations are carried and developed by small networks of dedicated actors, often outsiders or fringe actors (Geels and Schot, 2007). While this assures that sustainable alternatives are considered and acted upon, gathering wider support can be challenging within the context of a regime change (Hillman, Axon, & Morrissey, 2018). Tensions and contradictions may occur with incumbent regimes as opening niche opportunities emerge and niches start to drive regime transformations (Geels and Schot, 2007; Seyfang and Smith, 2007).

The transition from one regime to another involves a fundamental reordering and realignment of both the social and technical components of systems (Bolton & Hannon, 2016). According to the Strategic Niche Management (SNM) literature, niche innovations have a high failure rate when they emerge (van Eijck & Romijn, 2008). Structural change at the regime level can come from the incubation of ideas and experiences at the niche level (Berry, Davidson, & Saman, 2013). Successful niches are 'incubation rooms' within which innovating firms are supported both by private resources and public funding (Hillman et al., 2018). New technologies are protected against harsh selection competition and are provided with space to grow and mature through gradual experimentation and learning processes (Lopolito, Morone, & Sisto, 2011).

2.2 Nature of transition

Socio-technical systems are conceptualised as clusters of aligned elements, such as technical artefacts, knowledge, markets, regulation, cultural meaning, rules, infrastructure (Kern, 2012). A focus on regimes in the transitions literature recognises that organisations and technologies are embedded within wider social and economic systems (Rip & Kemp, 1998). As Socio-technical regimes have become the focal unit of analysis, the policy challenge is to transform them into more sustainable configurations (Smith et al., 2005).

The failure of many policies and management efforts to change the course of economic and societal systems toward more sustainable directions shows that there has been a lack of a sense of direction, vision and overall goal (Korhonen, 2007). It is increasingly apparent that current energy systems are unsustainable across a myriad of social, economic, and environmental criteria (Grübler, 2012). In addressing this, the Socio-technical approach to transitions is broader than other approaches to sustainable development (Geels, 2012). Critical to the development of STT theory are the concepts of technical regimes and the idea of technological paradigms and technological trajectories (Dosi, 1982). An energy transition is a switch from an economic system dependent on one or a series of energy sources and technologies to another (Crabbé et al., 2013). It is now widely recognized that an energy transition to a low-carbon economy based largely on renewable energy sources is necessary to meet the challenge of climate change and bring human activities back within ecological boundaries (Meadowcroft, 2009; Solomon & Krishna, 2011). The European Council has confirmed the European Union (EU) objective to reduce EU greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions by 80-95% compared to 1990 levels by 2050, in order to keep the global average temperature increase below 2°C (Capros et al., 2011).

The management aspects of transitions are strongly contested in the literature with opponents arguing that due to overriding issues of power and complexity involved, it is not possible to manage the dynamics of a transition (Shove & Walker, 2007). However proponents argue that 'transition management' is not management in the traditional sense, but is in effect more a process of 'steering' or facilitating transitional activities (Rotmans & Loorbach, 2009), involving the setting of goals, visions and pathways, and then adjusting, adapting, influencing, guiding and reflecting on these. Such an approach can enable identification of those characteristics which might best allow for a transition to develop (Alkemade, Hekkert, & Negro, 2011; Grin, Rotmans, & Schot, 2010). The development of centralised energy systems, the transition from piston engines to jetliners and the Dutch Forth National Environmental Policy Plan constitute examples of an applied transition management approach (Kemp et al., 2007). Key elements include (Kemp & Rotmans, 2009; Rotmans & Loorbach, 2008):

- Long-term thinking, including the setting of visions and goals, which informs short-term policy development;
- Multiple domains, actors and levels, including links to wider national and international policy development such as Kyoto protocol;
- The establishment of a transitions arena for technology and social innovation, program development and ongoing learning;
- Policy oriented towards system innovation besides system improvement (deep structural changes);
- Reflexive governance (periodic reviews and assessment) throughout the process to ensure that the transition is 'on track' and to avoid a lock-in of technologies and practices; and
- Identification and engagement of societal actors.

2.3 European dimension

The European Union has been to the fore in driving the current energy transition, with its goal of achieving low-carbon configurations, a role made more obvious given the United States' repeated abdication of any social, political or technological leadership on the topic. Policies relating to energy at the EU level have, in recent years, tended towards greater integration of internal energy markets across the member states in order to strengthen energy security and make it more affordable and sustainable; by fostering competition and providing stronger political leverage vis-à-vis reducing carbon emissions associated with climate change.

This position has been a result of a gradual process. European energy policy during the 1960s was framed very much at the nation state level with issues there taking a priority. This started to shift during the 1970s with the series of rapid oil shocks, especially in 1973 and 1974, demonstrating to policy makers the clear need to foster greater cooperation at the transnational level. This culminated member states agreeing to

move towards greater coordination and reciprocal exchanges, particularly in relation energy supply and demand in the early 1980s. In conjunction to these changing realities in global energy supply, the increasing importance of the environmental movement in raising awareness of the environmental costs associated with energy procurement and consumption began to make its presence felt in popular discourses across Europe. However, environmental concerns did start to inform policy – though still in quite modest terms – in 1987's Single European Act, which itself was the first major revision of the 1957 Treaty of Rome. In it, the European Community's shift further away from coal and steel concerns, and focus on establishing a single, common market for goods across member states by 1992. As part of this strategy, the nascent idea of an Internal Energy Market also began to form.

Environmental considerations were further pushed to the fore after 1990 with the first assessment report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) and the subsequent Earth Summit in Rio de Janeiro, Brazil, in 1992. The 1990s saw a greater shift towards mainstreaming environmental issues with the 1997 Kyoto Protocol locking member states into achieving real emissions-reductions targets by 2012 (UN, 1997). This also gave the European Union to put forward its clear intention to tackle climate change through its relationship with member states with more ambitious goals across the trading bloc with the target of becoming the global leader in tackling the energy emissions, climate change nexus. The European Commission's "An energy policy for Europe" (European Commission, 2007) marked the beginning of an even greater integrated approach to European energy policy. At its core, this energy package sets out the EU's stall, so to speak, with sustainability, security of supply and competitiveness highlighted as being of particular importance. As part of its Action Plan 2007-2009, the European Council adopted the 2020 climate & energy package (EU, 2008), commonly referred to as the 20-20-20 targets. The package sets out three key targets to be reached by 2020:

- 20% reduction in EU greenhouse gas emissions (below 1990 levels),
- 20% of EU energy consumption to come from renewable sources; and a
- 20% improvement on energy efficiency (culminating in a reduction in overall primary energy use)

A notable dimension to this package is the binding of member states to annual targets up to 2020 for cutting emissions under the "effort-sharing decision", under the Renewable Energy Directive (EU, 2009), with targets very much dependent on differing levels of national wealth. Through this mechanism, the richest member states face a cut of 20% to their emissions rate (compared to 2005 levels) and the least wealthy member states keep within a 20% increase of their emissions rate. While the least wealthy have the allowance to increase their emissions they will still be expected to make some effort to reduce limit those emissions in a more sustainable way.

Taking action in several areas to meet these targets, the EU established an Emissions Trading System (ETS) as a cornerstone to its policy to cut industrial greenhouse gas emissions cost-effectively and combat climate change. The system operates by placing a cap on overall emissions from covered installations, with this figure further reduced each year. Companies can buy and sell emission allowances as needed within this limit. This 'cap-and-trade' approach allows for greater operational flexibility on the part of the participating companies and is seen as more cost-effective than other alternatives. It was the first, and remains the largest, international system for trading greenhouse gas emission allowances in excess of some 11,000 power stations and industrial plants across 31 countries, as well as airlines operating between these countries and covers about 45% of the EU's total greenhouse gas emissions. Overall, this should help the EU meet its 2020 targets, while also achieving the desired 10% share of energy consumed in transport coming from renewable energy sources. In July 2015, the European Commission revised this scheme for its next phase (2021-2030), bringing it in line the EU's 2030 climate and energy policy framework with further reductions of ETS emissions by 43% compared to 2005 figures (European Commission, 2015b). Further key aspects include:

- A reduction of the overall number of allowances to an annual rate of 2.2% from 2021 onwards, compared to 1.74% up to 2021
- More dynamic and targeted allocations of free allowances, with:
 - continual updated benchmarks that reflect technological progress
 - focused carbon leakage classifications
 - better alignment of production levels to the free allocation allowances
- More support mechanisms to help industry and power sectors meet the innovation and investment targets set out to achieve the low-carbon energy transition, including an additional:
 - Innovation Fund that extends existing supports for demonstrating innovative technologies to industry actors; and a
 - Modernisation Fund that promotes investment in modernising existing power sector actors, along with improving energy efficiency in the 10 lower-income member states and the wider European energy system generally
- Maintaining the free allowance supports to help modernise the power sectors in the 10 lower-income member states

Figure 2 below shows the total trading volumes of EU emission allowances from 2005 to 2015. These combined figures account for the three key mechanisms used; auctions, over the counter (OTC) transactions and trading exchanges. Auctions remain the least used mechanism, with the majority of allowances divided between OTC and trading exchanges. 2013 marked a high watermark in the total number of allowances given to date. The EU ETS is making an important contribution toward the establishment of an international carbon

market, with national and regional systems already operating in China, the United States, Japan, South Korea, Canada, New Zealand, and Switzerland.

Figure 2: Total trading volumes in EU emission allowances (in millions of tonnes) 2005–2015

At present, the EU imports approximately 53% of all the energy it consumes, with six member states solely being reliant on one external supplier for all gas imports. Estimates on energy efficiency the domestic housing indicate that 75% of EU housing across the 27 member states is energy inefficient, with 94% of transport infrastructure relying on oil products, of which 90% are imported, to maintain functionality. Wholesale electricity and gas prices are (respectively) 30% and 100% higher than in they are in the United States (EU Council, 2018).

Further innovation and financing supports can be accessed through the EU’s NER300 programme for renewable energy technologies and carbon capture & storage and Horizon 2020 funding for research & innovation, with both programmes being arguably the two of the largest funding programmes of their kind, globally. NER 300 is seen as a catalyst for the demonstrating environmentally safe carbon capture and storage (CCS) and the development of novel renewable energy (RES) technologies to commercial scale within the trading bloc. With a budget of some €80 billion, made available from 2014 to 2010, the Horizon 2020 funding stream is the financial instrument of the EU’s Innovation Union, a Europe 2020 flagship initiative designed to improve Europe's global competitiveness.

Efforts to transition to economic models with significantly improved energy efficiency levels are also being heavily promoted, especially through the Energy Efficiency Plan and the 2012 Energy Efficiency Directive (updated 2016). The updated Energy Efficiency Directive includes the new 30% energy efficiency target for 2030 with additional measures to help ensure this new target is met. These comprise a series of new national measures that are targeted at both consumers and industry alike. Most notably,

- energy distributors and retail energy sales companies must achieve a minimum 1.5% energy savings per year through the implementation of energy efficiency measures;

- member states may opt to secure the same level of savings by other means, like improving the efficiency of heating systems in buildings, installing double glazed windows or insulating roofs etc.;
- the public sectors in each member state is required to favour the purchasing of energy efficient buildings, products and services over less energy efficient options;
- member state governments are required to carry out annual energy efficient renovations on at least 3% (by floor area) of the buildings they own and/or occupy;
- making it easier for energy consumers to access their data on consumption through individual metering is presented as helping to empower citizens to make better choices when managing their consumption;
- national incentives available for SMEs to undergo energy audits;
- large companies will make audits of energy consumption to help them identify ways to reduce it;
- monitoring efficiency levels in new energy generation capacities.”

In 2015, the European Commission also launched the Energy Union Strategy to help coordinate the various strands involved in transforming Europe’s energy supply infrastructure. European dependence on imported energy from and the need to develop its climate mitigation and adaptation strategies has led to the trading bloc committing itself to building a future-orientated climate policy in accordance with the European Commission’s framework strategy, and prioritising the following five key dimensions:

- Energy security, solidarity and trust;
- A fully integrated European energy market;
- Energy efficiency contributing to moderation of demand
- Decarbonising the economy; and
- Research, innovation and competitiveness.

A key political priority for the Commission is its strategy to reach a minimum 10% electricity interconnection for all member states by 2020, which it sees as being “crucial for sustainable development and decarbonising the energy mix as it enables the grid to accommodate increasing levels of variable renewables in a more secure and cost-efficient way” (European Commission, 2015a, p. 4). This, it is envisaged, will help to push down energy prices, reduce the need to build new power plants, minimise electrical grid instability, while at the same time improving the reliability of renewable energy supply. This year, 2018, a Commission proposal to invest a further €873 million in clean energy infrastructure – financed through the Connecting Europe Facility (CEF) and administered through the Innovation and Networks Executive Agency (INEA) – was agreed

by the EU member states. The CEF facilitates cross-border interactions between public administrations and businesses through a suite of financial instruments, including guarantees and project bonds from a total budget of €30.4 billion. INEA's budgetary allocation comprises €27.4 billion of this with €22.4 billion for Transport, €4.7 billion for Energy, and €0.3 billion for Telecom with projects applying under one of these three sectors. Another platform that has been established to enable EU-based project promoters, in both the public and private sectors, to attract potential international investors is the European Investment Project Portal (EIPP).

2.4 Need for new ways of doing business

In the built environment, radical transformation is not occurring sufficiently fast to meet environmental targets. Wainstein and Bumpus (2016, p. 572) attribute this inertia to an 'incumbent carbon lock-in trajectory'. Given the recognised need for widespread building renovation in the context of climate change and energy security issues, such inertia requires deeper analysis and understanding. An appropriate framework for explaining the reasons for barriers to widespread change is the multi-level perspective on sustainability transitions (Geels, 2011) augmented by co-evolutionary economic thinking. Using this framework, buildings and the building industry can be modelled as elements of a socio-technical system, defined as 'a seamless web of interlocking artefacts, institutions, organisations, natural resources, knowledge, etc. that combine to fulfil particular societal functions via production, distribution and consumption processes' (Geels, 2004, p. 898). Socio-technical systems are embedded in socio-technical regimes, i.e., 'the locus of established practices and associated rules (engineering beliefs, routines, heuristics, social expectations and visions) that stabilize existing systems' (Geels, 2011). Actors reproduce socio-technical systems, shaped and informed by the deep structure formed by socio-technical regimes (Geels, 2011, 2004). Such regimes constitute the accepted mainstream, institutionalised, means of delivering societal functions (Smith, Voß, & Grin, 2010). This structure encourages path dependent, incremental innovations, as opposed to disruptive radical innovations, thus lending stability to socio-technical systems and supporting the emergence of prevailing means by which particular societal functions are realised (Geels, 2004). Transitions of socio-technical systems imply (and necessitate) the reconfiguration of institutions, politics and decision-making (Jørgensen, 2012). However, innovations typically occur incrementally and develop along rather narrow trajectories, due to the considerable alignment of social and technical elements of regimes (Fuenfschilling & Truffer, 2014). A change in regimes implies a change in the system in which it functions. Regimes tend to resist systemic change and thus also innovation niches, which aim to replace regimes, or fundamentally alter regimes (Lachman, 2013). A transition from one socio-technical regime to another usually comes from external pressures offering windows of opportunities for mature innovations to challenge existing routines. Socio-technical regimes generally only shift from one paradigm to another when there is alignment of mature innovations with external pressures.

A socio-technical perspective on transition is appropriate for explaining the apparent disconnect between clear signs that a new energy paradigm is emerging and the apparent reluctance of built environment stakeholders to shift from existing operating models, many based on inherent assumptions of cheap, freely available energy. Considerable academic literature exists on the barriers to EE and RE technology uptake in the built environment. Chai and Yeo (2012), Pelenur and Cruickshank (2012) and Vogel *et al.* (2015) provide comprehensive reviews of research to date in this area. These barriers can be interpreted as a manifestation of the current locked-in regime (Wainstein and Bumpus, 2016). Table 2 presents a summary of commonly cited barriers to EE and RE uptake and interprets these through a socio-technical lens.

Table 2: Socio-technical perspective on barriers to energy efficiency and renewable energy

Barrier	Example	Source	Socio-technical Perspective
Political-institutional barriers	Lack of policy co-ordination or obstruction of reform	(Langlois-Bertrand, Benhaddadi, Jegen, & Pineau, 2015)	Actors with a stake in, or support from, dominant regime impede efforts to put on the agenda, elaborate, or successfully implement EE measures
Split-incentive issues	'landlord-tenant dilemmas' whereby Investments have to be made by the building owner, but lower energy bills benefit the tenant is identified as a major barrier	(Immendoerfer, Winkelmann, & Stelzer, 2014)	Lock-in and inertia effects whereby property investments have been made on the incumbent logic of the dominant (carbon intensive) regime, based on assumptions of cheap energy.
Financial barriers	Limited access to capital and cost disincentives	(Mosannenzadeh, Bisello, Diamantini, Stellin, & Vettorato, 2017)	Inertia effects of financier practices - insufficient external financial support and funding for project activities; perhaps due to low level of awareness or low level of return on investment when compared to 'carbon-intensive' investments
Lack of systematic approach	Piecemeal approaches overlook the interconnected nature of EE/RE related barriers	(Chai & Yeo, 2012)	EE & RE paradigm has not sufficiently challenged the incumbent built environment energy regime to offer a 'new version of normal'. EE and RE still not viewed as essential
Culture, behaviour and practices	Issues of lack of time; convenience; and forgetfulness, as impacts of the rebound effect	(Pelenur & Cruickshank, 2012)	Evidence of 'lock-in' effects in socio-cultural domain.
Risk aversion	May be linked to (or worsened by) imperfect information barriers, if the missing information is the one needed to make proper risk assessments.	(Langlois-Bertrand <i>et al.</i> , 2015)	Path-dependency of current regime structures suggest alternatives to the regime may carry higher risks (particularly financial) and clear organisational / legal protections may not be sufficiently developed.

Buildings and the built environment can therefore be conceptualised as elements of a socio-technical system that combine to fulfil particular societal functions. Such a structure encourages incremental innovations, rather than disruptive radical innovations, leading to stability in the regime but also to issues of path dependency, inertia and lock-in, as described in Table 2.

3 Value creation, delivery and capture

O’Cass & Ngo (2011) suggest that the ‘... *primary pursuit of any business is to understand what customers value and to create that value for them*’. This chapter examines this important concept of value, and explores the creation, delivery and capture of value, which are so central to business model design.

3.1 Value concepts

3.1.1 Defining value

The concept of value is at once quite straightforward, while at the same time being quite subjective. A dictionary would define value as “*the importance, worth, or usefulness of something*” or as “*the material or monetary worth of something*” (OUP, 2010). Morrissey, Dunphy and MacSweeney (2014) consider that value, in a business context, can be thought of as a preferred combination of benefits, compared with the costs of acquisition, or as Walters and Lancaster (1999) describe the value of goods and services as, “*the utility combination of benefits delivered to a customer less the total costs of acquiring the delivered benefits*”. There is however, a propensity for different meanings to be attached to the term ‘value’. For this reason, Bowman and Ambrosini (2000) find it useful to distinguish between the exchange value *i.e.*, monetary value realised by sale of a product and the use value *i.e.*, qualities of the product as perceived by the customer. Traditional economists (Neap & Celik, 1999) would explain customer decision-making through a rationalist frame of reference, positing that they determine the difference between the costs and the value they perceive *i.e.*, marginal value component of the price (for them). Others would argue that people are not simple utility maximising entities (so-called ‘*homo economicus*’) and point to the relevance of theories of bounded rationality (Simon, 1957), social practice (Pink, 2012; Shove & Walker, 2010), *etc.* in explain people’s decisions. But regardless of how one explains their decision-making process, the value placed customers places on products is of course entirely personalised and is based on their personal beliefs and values – termed by some as value systems⁵.

3.1.2 Value proposition

Walters & Lancaster (1999) posit that understanding how companies deliver value to their customers, in other words their value proposition, is important internally, as a means of identifying the value it is offering customers, and externally as a way to position itself and its products in customers’ minds. Lanning & Michaels (1988) argue that the formulation of a value proposition and development of a system to deliver it to customers, is the foundation of a successful business strategy. Value propositions establish and describe how features of products and services are assembled and offered in order to meet customers’ need. It is perhaps not unfair to characterise the traditional product focussed business approach as designing products and then persuading potential customers to buy them – general without a full understanding of what customers wanted. Lanning and Michaels (1988) reconceptualised the role of business as delivering value to customers

⁵ See (Narasimhan, Bhaskar, & Prakhya, 2010) for a good overview of concepts associated with personal value systems.

(as opposed to sale of products), and in doing so made the case for inverting the traditional logic – their thesis was that business needed to understand what prospective customers wanted before designing a product. In this value delivery system, the first step is selecting the value proposition. They acknowledge that companies often discover a successful business proposition only after the fact, but posit that “*what distinguish winners is that they do find, develop or recognise that winning proposition*” (Lanning & Michaels, 1988).

From Lanning and Michaels’ perspective, the value proposition should ideally reflected in every function of the firm, observing that “... *chances are improved the more that each element of the business reinforce the same objective*” (Lanning & Michaels, 1988). In this reconceptualization of business operations in terms of value delivery, Dunphy (2018) suggests that market research offers an interesting example: “Traditionally, it is fundamentally considered a marketing activity, principally influencing how a product is positioned on the marketplace – while, in the value delivery model, such knowledge of the market is instrumental in the creation of the value proposition and directly feeding into the design of product and services”. If business operations are to be framed in terms of delivering value, the description of business model offered by Osterwalder & Pigneur (2010) is particularly apt: the “rationale of how an organization creates, delivers, and captures value”. The following section shall explore the concept of business models, which may be from another perspective may be conceived as value delivery models.

3.2 The business model concept

3.2.1 Background

The business model is a nebulous, and indeed somewhat of a contested, concept – the literature is inconsistent in its use (Al-Debei & Avison, 2010; Magretta, 2002; Osterwalder, Pigneur, & Tucci, 2005). Business models are seen by Osterwalder and Pigneur (2002) as the ‘missing link’ between the strategy and operations of an organisation. While much attention has been paid to strategy (Porter, 1980) and to business operations (Guha, Kettinger, & Teng, 1993) in the literature, business model has largely been ignored until relatively recently⁶. The business model concept can be used as an analytical tool to better understand how a company does business, to assist in performance assessment, management, communication, and innovation (Bocken, Bakker, & de Pauw, 2016; George & Bock, 2011). Originating in the ‘dot-com’ era as a means of pitching business ideas and in the analysis of, and for, the Internet economy (Hayes & Finnegan, 2005), more recently the use of the business model concept has been expanded and applied in various fields such as: open source software (Feller, Finnegan, & Hayes, 2008), open innovation (Chesbrough, 2006), ‘long tail’ businesses (Anderson, 2006), smart grid (Bae, Kim, & Lim, 2010) and to an increasing extent sustainable innovation (Boons & Lüdeke-Freund, 2013).

⁶ Although there were occasional examples of the phrase being used for some time, for example Bellman et al., (1957) and Jones (1960).

3.2.2 Defining the concept

The term 'business model' is almost characterised by its ambiguity, or as Porter (2001) quips "*the definition of a business model is murky at best*". However, the term itself instinctively conveys a rudimentary understanding, implying a representation of a company's dealings. As alluded to above, there are multiple perspectives on business models, which has led to diversity of definitions in the literature *e.g.*,

"depicts the content, structure, and governance of transactions designed so as to create value through the exploitation of business opportunities" (Amit & Zott, 2001)

"description of how your company creates value for customers that in turn generated revenue and profits for your company" (Tucker, 2001)

"abstract representation of some aspect of a firm's strategy; it outlines the essential details one needs to know to understand how a firm can successfully deliver value to its customers" (Seddon & Lewis, 2003).

(Christensen, Anthony, & Rot, 2004; Osterwalder, 2004; Osterwalder et al., 2005; Shafer, Smith, & Linder, 2005; Teece, 2010; Timmers, 1998; Wirtz, 2011).

Wirtz (2011) distinguished three schools of thought during the development of the business model concept: the first stream involves the development of new ways of doing business. The second stream concerns organisational theory and positions the business model as a strategic management tool. While the third stream builds on this management tool, adding the element of market competition to the efficiency focus. The basis for this third stream of business models is that creating and delivering customer value is central to a business model. Wirtz notes that in creating and developing unique value propositions for customers, business models can themselves become a competitive advantage with novel developed business models being the means by which companies execute their market strategies. Observing this phenomenon, Casadesus-Masanell & Ricart (2010) opine that "*a business model is a reflection of a firm's realized strategy*".

Taking into account the diverse view on the 'business model' concept, the most widely accepted understanding of what the 'business model' concept constitutes is reflected by Osterwalder and Pigneur's (2010) view that "*a business model describes the rationale of how an organisation creates, delivers and captures value*".

3.2.3 Understanding business models

Boons & Lüdeke-Freund (2013), building on the work of Osterwalder (2004) and Doganova & Eyquem-Renault (2009), forwarded the following four components of a generic business model:

- Value proposition: what value is embedded in the product/ service offered;
- Supply chain: how upstream relationships are structured and managed;
- Customer interface: how are downstream relationships with customers structured and managed;
- Financial model: how costs and benefits are distributed across stakeholders.

Building on the ideas forwarded in his seminal thesis (2004), Osterwalder worked to develop, refine and codify the concepts embodied in his original business model ontology. The result of this work has been the so-called business model canvas (Osterwalder & Pigneur, 2010), a visual chart which serves as an entrepreneurial tool facilitating the description, design, challenge, invention, and reinvention of business models. The canvas identified nine building blocks of business models as detailed below.

- Customer Segments: particular customers that a company aims to serve with its value proposition;
- Value Propositions: goods and services that constitute its offering for a target customer segment;
- Channels: means to communicate with and satisfy customer segment demand from value propositions;
- Customer Relationships: outline of the different relationships with target customer segments;
- Revenue streams: income generated from each customer segment;
- Key resources: most important assets required for a company to actualise its business model;
- Key activities: most important things for a company to accomplish for its business model to succeed;
- Key Partners: network of partners and suppliers that make the business model work;
- Cost Structure: costs incurred to operate a business model.

Figure 3 below illustrates the constituents of the business model. Osterwalder and Pigneur (2010) explain their relationship as follows: companies serve one or more **customer segments** (2), by solving their needs with **value propositions** (1), which are delivered through communication, distributions and sales **channels** (3). Throughout these interactions, **customer relationships** (4) are established and maintained and **revenue streams** (9) result from each value proposition successfully offered. In delivering the value proposition **key resources** (6) are utilised to perform a number of **key activities** (5) within the company and working with **key partners** (7) through the outsourcing of certain activities and acquisition of some resources. The previous outlined eight elements define the **cost structure** (8) of the business model.

Figure 3: Business model components (adapted from Dunphy & Morrissey, 2015, p. 17)

3.3 Business model innovation

Zott and Amit (Zott & Amit, 2010) posit that the “overall objective of a focal firm’s business model is to exploit a business opportunity by creating value for the parties involved”. Innovation in business models is therefore at the core of creating and realising new business opportunities. Savic (Savic, 2014) posits that new business models have the greatest impact in the economic sense and to society in general. In an era of disruptive innovation, business models no longer have a lengthy ‘shelf-life’. This means that firms will need to engage in a continuous process of radical business model innovation. As discussed in ENTRUST deliverable 2.3, the concept of innovation is often conflated with related terms such as creativity, change, or invention. In D3.4, Boo, Molinero, *et al.* (Boo et al., 2017) explain that innovation results in intentional positive change through the delivery of original novelty to the marketplace (or society). The objective of this report is to outline novel business models, which in offering target customers a desired value proposition, do so in a manner which contributes to the energy transition. This is in keeping with the idea of ‘business models innovations for sustainability’, which Bocken, Short, Rana, & Evan (2014) define as those which “create significant positive and/or significantly reduced negative impacts for the environment and/or society, through changes in the way the organisation and its value-network create, deliver value and capture value (i.e. create economic value) or change their value propositions”.

The ‘Ten types of innovation’ framework (Keeley, Walters, Pikkell, & Quinn, 2013) offers a means of identifying new business opportunities and develop viable innovative business models. The outline of the framework is shown in Table 3 below.

Table 3: Ten Types of Innovation (Keeley et al., 2013)

Configuration	Offering	Experience
<i>Profit model</i> : innovation related to what to offer, charge, or how to collect revenues.	<i>Product performance</i> : innovation associated with new features and functionality on products.	<i>Service</i> : innovation focused on enhancing utility, performance, and value of an offering.
<i>Network</i> : innovative connections between companies to share capabilities and create synergies.		<i>Channel</i> : innovation in links and connections between companies and customers.
<i>Structure</i> : innovation focused on organising company assets to create added-value.	<i>Product system</i> : innovation rooted in how products and services are bundled together.	<i>Brand</i> : Innovation based on developing identity that attracts buyers.
<i>Process</i> : innovation in the operations and processes that deliver offerings to customers.		<i>Customer engagement</i> : innovation in the means by which customers are engaged.

The ‘Business Model Innovation Grid’, a sustainability tool created by the Flanders circular economy hub, describes eight archetypes of innovation, as shown in Table 4 below.

Table 4: Business Model Innovation Grid

Technology	Social	Organisation
Optimisation of resources	Functionality, not ownership,	Co-creation - knowledge sharing
Circularity of wastes	Stewardship- stakeholder engagement	Social entrepreneurship
Substitution ‘greener’ options	Slow consumption	

In the aforementioned earlier output, Boo, Molinero, *et al.* (2017) combined elements of the above frameworks to identify and categorise business model innovation in the energy system. This ENTRUST classification of innovation outlined in Table 5 below offers a useful approach to understand the type of innovations that could be implemented in businesses to make that more aligned with the transition to a more sustainable low-carbon energy society.

Table 5: ENTRUST Business Model Innovation Categories (Boo et al., 2017)

Configuration	Technology	Experience	Financing
Profit Model	Optimisation	Product service system	Financial instruments and payment schemes
Vertical Value Chain Integration	Circularity	Customer engagement	
Partnership	Substitution with renewable resources	Channel innovations	
		Integration	

3.4 Towards novel business models

This section introduced ideas surrounding value creation, delivery and capture, discussed their relationship to business model concept, and outlined the types of innovation in business models which can contribute to fostering the energy transition. Many of business models relevant to the energy transition are associated with new or pre-existing structures or facilities. As background to the business models presented later, Section 4 gives an overview of a selection of arrangements used to structure projects. The following Section 0 forwards examples of business models, which may have the potential foster the energy transition – with a particular focus on public-private partnerships and community based approaches. These business models relate to three sectors which are seen as offering significant potential in fostering transition, namely: (i) energy production and supply; (2) built environment; (3) shared mobility. The business model are described; graphically presented using the ENTRUST canvas first presented in Boo, Molinero, *et al.* (Boo et al., 2017) and shown in Figure 4 below; and their contribution to fostering transition outlined.

Figure 4: ENTRUST Business Canvas (Boo et al., 2017)

4 Project delivery methods

4.1 Introduction

The variety of choice open to us today with regards to type of business model one chooses to use for a given project is enormous. This spectrum of choice ranges from for-profit, venture-backed corporations to small-scale cooperative collectives and everything in between. How local communities are able to leverage this choice will, in many ways, determine the relative success or failure of policy makers to realise a just and fair energy transition that also helps to offset the worst effects of human induced climate change. The new range of businesses reshaping our business landscape are very much linked in to the so-called ‘sharing economy’ (Hamari & Ukkonen, 2013; Schor, 2016). While some see this new sharing economy approach as helping to reduce environmental consumption and neutralise income inequality in reality, the emerging sharing landscapes are very complex. Having said that they still do provide local communities, who have heretofore seen the agency reduced to passive consumers of a limited range of produce, with the opportunity to address these issues in a meaningful and proactive way. Section 4 presents the key approaches that, as we see them, could offer this opportunity.

4.2 Public private partnerships (PPP)

Reflecting their growth and the “vast array of activities” they describe, there is a range of definitions of public-private partnerships (Hodge, Greve, & Biygautane, 2018, p. 2). A public-private partnership (PPP) is broadly understood as a business arrangement that takes the form of a long-term contractual agreement between the public and private sectors. The OECD defines PPPs as a ‘long term contractual arrangements between the government and a private partner whereby the latter delivers and funds public services using a capital asset, sharing the associated risk’ (OCED, 2012, p. 18). These public services would have traditionally been provided and financed by government, however PPPs have become an increasingly popular means of delivering both services, and in particular infrastructure, globally, and are considered to be “an important and innovative part of today’s public infrastructure agenda” (Hodge & Greve, 2018). Promising more “value for money”, the rationale for the use of PPPs is that, when properly implemented, they “are said to produce reduced life-cycle costs, better risk allocation, faster implementation of public works and services, improved service quality and additional revenue streams” (Renda & Schrefler, 2006).

In the European context, PPPs have become an integral element of the EU strategic policy development for growth. Increasingly, EU institutions are expanding the role of the private sector in the delivery of public services and they have “intellectually invested in creating legal, economic and policy systems” to facilitate this development (Bovis, 2010).

Viewed as strategically important, PPPs are promoted by the European Commission and they have become an “an instrument of modern public sector management, with attractive consequences resulting from the methods of financing and the risk allocation mechanisms deployed in the relevant relations between public

and private sectors” (Bovis, 2010). While it can be argued that the enthusiasm for PPPs from the EC, as well as that of the World Bank and the IMF follows their historical enthusiasm for “outsourcing and privatisation” (Contemporary public-private partnership: Towards a global research agenda (Hodge & Greve, 2017), Bovis maintains that PPPs “represent a credible solution for the delivery of public services in the 21st century EU and its Member States” (Bovis, 2010).

The need for European governments to implement energy efficiency projects to meet the targets fixed in the European Energy Policy Plan (20-20-20) in conjunction with public budgetary constraints and the requirement to keep within strict public expenditure limits has created a positive environment for the adoption of PPPs in the development of energy efficiency projects. Taking the form of Energy Performance Contracting (EPC), the public sector enters into an arrangement with an Energy Service Company (ESCO) to carry out activities connected to the delivery of energy services.

However, there remains significant potential for the development and adoption of PPPs in the arena of energy services. Carbonara and Pellegrino (Carbonara & Pellegrino, 2018) identify two problematic areas hampering the implementation of the model, the ‘dilemma of equally sharing the benefits’ between the public and private partners, and the lack of ‘adequate public procedures’ to ensure the selection of the most suitable EPC for the particular project (Carbonara & Pellegrino, 2018). Outlining the necessity for a “win-win” scenario narrowly focussed on monetary values where the requirements for profitability for the private sector partner and the economic interests of the public sector are balanced, Carbonara and Pellegrino propose an economic model that assesses and benchmarks the net benefits of three different EPC structures through the Net Present Value (NPV) method to support decision-making in the choice of the most appropriate EPC schema (*Ibid.*).

4.3 Community-based business models

Community-based business models are focussed on providing a range of benefits to the community rather than being restricted to economic benefits. CBBs incorporate holistic approaches to business that prioritise broader community gains as well as the provision of local employment and strengthening the local economy. Key attributes of community enterprises are that any assets are community owned, they are community led, and community controlled (Gibson, 2016). Community-based enterprises have the potential to attain an economy of scale that can ensure they are self-sustaining, guaranteeing their survival, and providing economic surpluses that are fed-back into the community. Their status as community-owned enterprises mitigates against potential negative local attitudes and objections to their operation.

Community-based enterprises have the potential to make a considerable contribution towards the transition towards renewable and sustainable energy, and in particular to the decentralisation of the energy system. The decentralisation of the energy system can potentially offer communities the opportunity to becoming self-sufficient in energy. Communities ranging from small villages to larger towns and cities have been

envisioning and developing pathways to achieving the production of 100% sustainable energy as well as energy neutrality and zero carbon emissions (Van Der Schoor & Scholtens, 2015). Recognising the potential transformation of communities and neighbourhoods that the energy transition portends, as well as the potential for negative community reception of renewable energy infrastructure and developments, community participation by means of CBBs could encourage both community ‘buy-in’ as well as progressing the decentralisation of the sustainable energy system. Emphasising the necessity for the equitable distribution of benefits in communities, as well as for ‘meaningful and substantial’ local involvement in energy projects, research from Walker and Devine-Wright shows that in the absence of benefit-sharing among the local community, renewable energy developments can become controversial and locally divisive (Walker & Devine-Wright, 2008).

In their investigation on how bottom-up, grass-roots transitions are developed from ‘local networks’ of committed and engaged citizens Van Der Schoor & Scholtens (Van Der Schoor & Scholtens, 2015) highlight local energy initiatives in the Netherlands, finding that for the “the development of a shared vision, the level of activities and the type of organisation are important factors of the strength of the ‘local network’”.

4.4 Social enterprises

‘Social enterprise’ is a term that describes a range of organisations seeking market-based solutions to social problems (Hillman et al., 2018). Sitting within the ‘third sector’ of the economy, social enterprises have both business and social goals, and they straddle the borders of both charity and business, combining aspects of both (Ebrahim, Battilana, & Mair, 2014). Typically they exist “where market or governmental failures exist in the provision of social welfare, and have increasingly become a key driver of social progress. The autonomous nature of the social-economic model applied by such organisations can represent a viable means to reduce state social welfare dependence, and is a proven model for social change” (Hillman et al., 2018, p. 447).

Social enterprises focus on achieving economic sustainability balanced with providing a social dividend. Their main source of revenue tends to be commercial, and they rely on commercial activity instead of charitable donations both to operate the business, as well as to scale-up their operations (Ebrahim et al., 2014). In contrast to the focus on developing mechanisms for balancing financial rewards between public and private partners in PPPs offered by Carbonara and Pellegrino (2018) where the value assessed is restricted to the economic, and the promised ‘win-win’ is thus limited to the economic value also, the ‘win-win’ offered by social enterprises are both social and economic. However, as Hillman *et al.* (2018) point out, not only do social enterprises and other community driven approaches remain significantly underexplored as “serious instruments of the sustainability transition”, they potentially offer “‘win-win-win’ outcomes across social, economic and ecological domains”. Social enterprises as form have the potential to be strong drivers of the low-carbon transition at community level, in particular with regard to the energy sector.

4.5 Crowdsourcing

Crowdsourcing is a business model that consists of three novel elements. First, it develops an ‘*open business model*’ that is open to incorporating contributions to processes and resources from “external creators”; second, crowdsourcing platforms “*leverage technology*” to exploit social networks and other media to invite

users to participate in “value creation activities”; third, the company facilitates the process of value creation by transferring “*value-creating activities*” to crowd members ensuring that the crowd “co-create value” by taking on a number of activities (Kohler, 2015).

Crowdsourcing can be conceptualised in terms of creating a virtual rather than a geographic community of members. However, crowdsourcing platforms have had a chequered history, most have been unsuccessful as enterprises – difficult to launch, to sustain and to enlarge (Kohler, 2015). The key elements that are necessary for a successful crowdsourcing business model requires them “to focus their activities on enabling creation, curation, and consumption” by their customer/co-creator base (Kohler, 2015). Fundamentally different to traditional business models and “producer-consumer transactions”, crowdsourcing “raises a new set of strategic choices related to how value is created and captured” (Kohler, 2015).

5 Orientating business models towards the transition

The aim of this section is to forward examples of business models, which may have the potential foster the energy transition – with a particular focus on public-private partnerships and community based approaches. In achieving this, needless to say, the reports is informed by work conducted earlier in the project, which concentrated on: understanding energy system stakeholders (Dallamaggiore et al., 2016)⁷ and energy system technologies (Landini, Zerbi, Morrissey, & Axon, 2016)⁸; appreciating the complexity of people’s relationship with energy (Dunphy, Revez, Gaffney, Lennon, et al., 2017)⁹ and associated technologies (Dunphy, Revez, Gaffney, & Lennon, 2017)¹⁰; and in mapping and analysing the policy and regulatory context (Boo et al., 2016; Salel et al., 2016)^{11,12}.

In addition, this deliverable is complementary to, and draws upon three deliverables, introduced earlier, which deal specifically with innovation and business models in the energy transitions, namely: Boo, Molinero, *et al.* (2017), which identified and characterised novel business models and the main barriers within the EU energy system; Morrissey, Axon, *et al.*, (2017), which examined innovation pathways for the energy transition; and Lennon, Dunphy, *et al.*, (2018), which explored energy management approaches for sustainable communities.

This section forwards ideas for business models in three economic domains which are considered to be particularly relevant for fostering the energy transition. These are: energy production and supply; energy-focused renovation of the built environment; and shared mobility. For each of these three areas, the potential contribution towards the energy transition will be characterised, particular barriers and challenges in achieving these contributions identified, and finally example business models which over these challenges outlined.

5.1 Energy Production and Supply

There is a growing acceptance that the transition away from an energy system based on fossil fuels will involves more than just switching energy sources. The established highly-centralised models of energy generation and distribution are being challenged, consumers are being required to play a more active role in

⁷ Dallamaggiore, E., Boo, E., Aze, F., Lennon, B., MacSweeney, R., Gaffney, C., Dunphy, N., Landini, A., Otal, J., 2016. Energy System Stakeholder Characterisation. ENTRUST Deliverable 2.1.

⁸ Landini, A., Zerbi, T., Morrissey, J., Axon, S., 2016. *Energy Technological Review*. ENTRUST Deliverable 2.2.

⁹ Dunphy, N.P., Revez, A., Gaffney, C., Lennon, B., Ramis Aguilo, A., Morrissey, J., Axon, S., 2017. *Intersectional Analysis of Energy Practices*. ENTRUST Deliverable 3.2.

¹⁰ Dunphy, N.P., Revez, A., Gaffney, C., Lennon, B., 2017. *Intersectional Analysis of Perceptions and Attitudes Towards Energy Technologies*. ENTRUST Deliverable 3.3.

¹¹ Boo, E., Pasqualini, T., Dallamaggiore, E., Dunphy, N.P., Lennon, B., Meade, K., Chichinato, O., Axon, S., Otal, J., 2016. *Policy & regulation landscape*. ENTRUST Deliverable 4.1.

¹² Aze, F., Dallamaggiore, E., Salel, M., Boo, E., Dunphy, N., Gaffney, C., Revez, A., Axon, S., Otal, J., Chichinato, O., Melchiorre, T., Costantini, V., 2016. *Europeanisation of national policy dialogues on energy pathways*. ENTRUST Deliverable 4.2.

managing their own energy usage, and most-importantly the public acceptance, both politically on a national level and specifically in the locale of proposed developments will be required for the successful roll-out of the renewable energy and associated infrastructure necessary for the move away from fossil fuels. While the scale and nature of the changes to established energy systems, and of citizen participation in that transition, remain open questions – it is clear that in democratic societies (at least), successful energy transitions require citizens to embrace the transition as something of which they are a part, rather than external impositions. This in turn requires modes of governance which are inclusive and participatory, and which allow all citizens to become full stakeholders in the transition and share in its benefits.

Achieving the goals of the Energy Union will require the social acceptance (and acceptability) of the energy and related project required to decarbonise our energy supplies. However, many such projects encounter strong public opposition, to an extent that threatens to significantly slow down Europe’s energy transition (Cohen, Reichl, & Schmidthaler, 2014; Enevoldsen & Sovacool, 2016). The Energy Roadmap 2050 argues that ‘The current trend, in which nearly every energy technology is disputed and its use or deployment delayed, raises serious problems for investors and puts energy system changes at risk’ (EC, 2011). In this regard community-based locally-focussed energy projects offer significant advantages in developing acceptability into prospective energy projects from the start through increased local participation, and more relevant, accessible and responsive communication, which will result in perceptions of, and realisation of, greater procedural and distributional justice in the implementation of the projects. More widespread adoption of community-based energy projects will increase the many existing municipalities, communities and social actors across Europe who have voluntarily embraced the role of transition leaders and ‘prosumers’ and in doing so increasing acceptability of such infrastructure projects.

In ENTRUST deliverable 5.3, Lennon, Dunphy *et al.*, (Lennon et al., 2018) forwarded five scenarios for community-based energy projects, characterising each scenario in terms of:

- Ownership of assets *i.e.*, was the project and its assets owned by an external commercial company? local community? local businesses? *etc.*
- Control of operations *i.e.*, who had control over the day-to-day operations of the project, was it an outside commercial company, a state body, a local co-operative, or a combination thereof. How were decision made – was it shareholder based? democratically controlled? other?
- Organisational types *e.g.*, state owned, locally-owned via municipality, commercial company, locally-owned via commercial company, producer co-operative, consumer-co-operative, combination, *etc.*
- Focus of activities *i.e.*, was the project’s activities focus on energy generation, was is more control with distribution of energy? Was it integrated utility? Did it supply to final consumers?
- Objectives of project *i.e.*, What was the principal aim of the project? return on investment (Profit)? affordable energy? Energy security? Economic development? Environmental sustainability? *etc.*
- Connectivity *i.e.*, did the project have a connection to the national grid? Was there a microgrid? other? Was there energy storage? *etc.*

This recent emergence of a growing cohort of small-scale electricity producers, that also continue to consume from the grid, presents a number of potential opportunities and challenges to individuals, communities and the energy systems that accommodate them. With the increasing number of households across Europe installing renewable energy production systems, such as photovoltaic (PV) panels, and small-scale wind and water turbines, there is a strong opportunity for community groups to capitalise on this trend by coming together into prosumer cooperatives¹³. These types of cooperatives can act on a number of levels, by increasing the collective bargaining power of individual prosumer stakeholders who can negotiate more favourable contractual arrangements than would be otherwise possible. Also, they can contribute to generating the critical mass needed to radical reconfigure existing energy networks to better accommodate the renewable energy technologies that will ultimately realise the transition to a low-carbon economy. Recent developments such as in-home storage and peer-to-peer exchanges at the neighbourhood level are also making a growing contribution to the transition (Bellekom, Arentsen, & van Gorkum, 2016).

Earlier capitalist arrangements, largely shaped by varying intersecting producer and consumer models can be framed within the prosumption narrative, especially given the types of control and exploitation that occurred. In its latest iteration, prosumption capitalism has seen a noticeable return towards unpaid rather than paid labour, with an added dimension of products also often being offered at little or no cost. Also notable, is the systemic shift towards a mass abundance of goods and products, where once this would have been characterised by scarcity, which itself can be understood as a means of control. This similarity to earlier prosumer models suggests we are returning to this form of capitalism (Ritzer & Jurgenson, 2010), a not so unlikely prospect given the continued failures of neoliberal capitalism. Prosumption, in energy terms, usually refers to the combined production and consumption of electricity by small-scale operations. This is a break from existing models of production and consumption that have characterised business models up to recently. Some have argued that we are witnessing a return to prosumer capitalism, which was largely disrupted by the highly-centralised industrial configurations in operation from the 1800s to the present, across a number of key sectors and is in part driven by the shift to online user-generated content creation (Ritzer & Jurgenson, 2010). The following business models highlight how energy production and supply can be better incorporated into the energy transition by harnessing the full potential of community-led schemes, especially relating to the application of renewable energy cooperatives. In keeping with the cooperative movement more generally, renewable energy coops can take on several different forms. They include:

- Cooperatives that pool their investments collectively to build large scale projects that generate electricity to be sold directly to the national grid, and availing of nationally-structured buy-schemes such as feed-in tariffs etc.

¹³ For a more information on prosumer energy and prosumer power cooperatives see Pietkiewicz (2016).

- Cooperatives that develop small scale projects that then earn revenue by selling generated electricity to a third-party energy distributor, with profits are shared amongst members.
- Cooperatives that partner with energy developers. The developer takes on the major share of financial risk sourcing funding and negotiating with energy distributors, while cooperative members (usually landowners) take on a minority share in the project by providing assets, especially land, to support the project. Rural landowners might find this model especially useful for maximising bargaining power with developers and prioritising landowners' interests.
- Less common, though increasing in popularity, are private interests adopting the cooperative model, for example a RES developer working with landowners to reduce system costs through bulk purchasing and turn-key installations

An example of a renewable energy coops has been highlighted in D5.3, *Scenario 3: A Locally-Owned Renewable Energy Project*, and outlines how local community setup their own RES project and were able to contribute to other aspects of the energy transition, insulation of existing housing stock, in addition to generating renewable energy.

BM1: Renewable Energy Cooperative (RES-Coop small scale producer)

In this business model, a local community forms a cooperative society to develop the opportunity to contribute to the energy transition by offering them the opportunity to produce electricity that feeds directly into the electricity grid. By setting up a RES-Coop, members of a local community can avail of funding streams otherwise unavailable to them as individuals. Any surpluses arising from cooperative activities are redistributed amongst its members in accordance with established rules set down by that cooperative (as opposed to the amount of business each member does with the cooperative).

Figure 5 BM1: Renewable energy cooperative

Innovation: This type of business model moves away from traditional demand and supply models that have been captured by large scale energy actors, who continue to dominate the market. By using a renewable energy cooperative business model local community actors shift their position as largely ineffectual consumers of energy to having more proactive engagements with the energy system. They can also directly contribute to the energy transition at multiple points in the transition, from the generation of energy to climate change mitigation measures such as insulating existing housing stock.

BM2: Social, Public and Private Partnership (SPPP)

Social–Public–Private Partnerships (SPPP) are based on the public-private partnership (PPP) model. The SPPP is a business arrangement that takes the form of a long-term contractual agreement between a member of the ‘third sector’ – either a geographical community or a social enterprise or both – and the public and private sectors to provide energy infrastructure or an energy efficiency project. A local community forms a co-operative society drawing members from the community and/or geographical area to engage as equal partners with the public and private sector actors. SPPPs are assessed on an expanded basis in comparison to both PPPs and CPPPs. In addition to assessing risks and benefits in purely economic terms where the assessment is limited to financial considerations, the assessment of value extends to social value also. The assessment of risks and benefits also extends beyond the financial to include consideration of the social impacts and the risks and benefits to the community.

Figure 6 BM2: Social, Public and Private Partnership

Innovation: The innovation of the SPPP is that the community partner is incorporated into the process as an equal partner in a tripartite arrangement to provide energy infrastructure and/or energy management services wherein the community occupies the same status in the model as the public and private sector. A further innovation is that the assessment of risks and benefits extends beyond the financial implications to include a social value element where social impact is a factor to be included in the assessment of risk and return on any particular project.

BM3: Community and Public Private Partnership (CPPP)

Community-Public-Private Partnerships (CPPP) are based on the public-private partnership (PPP) model. The CPPP is a business arrangement that takes the form of a long-term contractual agreement between the community and the public and private sectors to provide infrastructure or an energy efficiency project. Local communities form a co-operative society drawing members from the community and/or geographical area to engage as equal partners with the public and private sector actors.

CPPPs are assessed on same basis as PPPs, that is in economic terms where the assessment of risks and benefits is solely limited to financial considerations. Economic benefits are shared with the community partner on the same basis as the public and private partners.

As with PPPs, CPPPs could be used to provide large scale energy infrastructure such as wind or solar farms, for example.

Figure 7 BM3: Community and Public Private Partnership

Innovation: The innovation of the CPPP is that the community partner is incorporated into the process as an equal partner in a tripartite arrangement to provide energy infrastructure or energy management services. The community occupies the same status in the model as the public and private actors.

BM4: Community Micro-enterprise Partnerships (CMPs)

Working with a local development association, a skills-orientated partnership is established to leverage the different skills of people living in the area that supports the establishment of energy-related micro-enterprises commensurate with those skills. These skills, in turn can contribute to the rolling out of energy-related projects at the household level. From the installation of locally sourced insulating materials (that meet national standards) into existing housing stock to the upcycling household electronic equipment, local homeowners can improve the energy efficiency of their homes by tapping into the pool of local knowledge. Members pay a small fee to the partnership to access information and participate in training courses, with the local development association offering supports in relation to grants and funding applications to the partnership. The partnership, in turn, channels this funding into delivering a range of standardised training courses for its members. The development association offers other supports such as the provision of training facilities, identifies appropriate trainers *etc.* from its pre-existing social and business networks, while the micro-enterprises supplement the incomes of the participants.

Figure 8 BM4: Community Micro-enterprise Partnerships

Innovation: This skills-orientated partnership empowers local people to leverage their skillsets to establish microenterprises that can in turn supplement their existing incomes. This is particularly useful in rural communities where traditional farming-related activities may not generate the same level of income it did in the past. It is innovative on a number of levels, most notably in terms of the classification of innovation referred to in *D2.3 Report on novel business models and main barriers in the EU energy system*, offering a novel partnership approach that sees existing pools of knowledge within the community being leveraged to creating new business environments with the establishment of micro-enterprises. It also contributes to the development of new PSS-functionality, with the emergent micro-enterprises offering a suite of services that satisfy users' needs, in this case filling the knowledge gap, rather than a physical product that can be produced more cheaply elsewhere.

5.2 Built Environment

Despite its significance as a core enabler of modern human life, there are significant negative aspects to the built environment. In particular, the built environment is responsible for up to two-fifths of energy consumption and accounts for *ca.* one-third of releases of climate changing gases (Cheng, Pouffary, Svenningsen, & Callaway, 2008; European Commission, 2010). It is clear that buildings have a significant contribution to make in achieving climate change objectives, given this significant share of global energy use and greenhouse gas emissions. As a consequence, perhaps more than any other single domain, buildings are perceived as representing one of the largest sources of unrealised potential cost effective energy savings and GHG reductions within Europe (European Commission, 2011; Staniaszek, Bruel, Fong, & Lees, 2013).

However, buildings are long-life products (European Commission, 2010; Kelly, 2009) with a low replacement rate for (Thomsen & van der Flier, 2009). It is estimated that four-fifths of buildings in the EU, currently in use will still be operational in 2030 (European Commission, 2010). This longevity of the building stock means that achieving the ambitious GHG emissions reduction targets for buildings sector (EU, 2008) requires not only new buildings of (very) high standards of energy efficiency, but also a substantial programme of energy renovation of existing buildings.

It is recognised that although there are strong societal pressures, regulatory drivers, economic pressures and technical supports encouraging building energyrenovation projects (Kneifel, 2010), the level of activity is far too low to achieve the level of energy savings expected of the sector. The European Commission notes that *“Energy efficiency in buildings suffers from underinvestment and numerous barriers”* (2016, p. 5). For the time being, at least, the level energy-focused renovation of buildings remains too low (European Commission, 2011), and the market for such renovation has not realised its full potential.

Levine et al., (2007) leveraging the work of Grubb & Wilde (2005) present four categories of barriers to energy performance improvement renovation of building, namely: Financial costs/benefits; Hidden costs/benefits; Market failures; and Behavioural and organisational inefficiencies. Table 6 below presents an overview of these different barriers that hinder energy efficient building intervention take up.

Barrier Categories	Definitions	Examples
Financial costs/benefits	Ratio of investment cost to value of energy savings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Higher up-front costs for more efficient equipment; • Lack of access to financing; • Energy subsidies; • Lack of internalisation of environmental, health and other external costs.
Hidden costs/benefits	Cost or risks (real or perceived) that are not captured directly in financial flows	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Costs and risks due to potential incompatibilities, performance risks, transaction costs <i>etc.</i>; • Poor power quality (i.e., electric supply with voltage, current and frequency values within optimum range), particularly in some developing countries.
Market failures	Market structures and constraints that prevent the consistent trade-off between specific energy-efficient investment and the energy saving benefits	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Limitations of the traditional building design process; • Fragmented market structure; • Landlord/tenant split and misplaced incentives; • Administrative and regulatory barriers (<i>e.g.</i>, in the incorporation of distributed generation technologies); • Imperfect information.
Behavioural and organisational inefficiencies	Behavioural characteristics of individuals and organisational characteristics of companies that hinder energy efficiency technologies and practices	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tendency to overlook multiple small energy conservation opportunities; • Organisational failures (<i>e.g.</i>, internal split incentives); • Non-payment and electricity theft; • Tradition, behaviour, lack of awareness and lifestyle; • Corruption.

Table 6: Taxonomy of barriers to energy efficient building technologies (*Levine et al., 2007, p. 419 derived from Grubb & Wilde 2005 p. 16*)

There is accordingly a need for innovative building models to deliver energy efficiency new buildings but more importantly to renovate existing building to a high standards of energy performance.

BM5: Public Private Modularised Building (PPMB)

A social housing association decides to leverage its number of members to get a better deal on a new housing scheme they are proposing. They engage with a construction company that offers off-site, pre-fabricated construction options to this building project. The approach taken by the company enables the social housing association to maximise its economy of scale advantage, in order to build better quality, affordable housing at a fraction of the time needed for traditional builds. Costs can also be curtailed as a result of this streamlining, while at the same time improving the living standards of its members. It also ensures that its members are not waiting longer for building completion and the accumulated social costs this involves. This business model offers local communities an opportunity to contribute to the energy transition by enabling them to select better energy design and energy efficient construction methods when embarking on a new building project and can be used across a range of building activities including one-off housing, multi-unit private and social housing developments.

Figure 9 BM5: Public Private Modularised Building

Innovation: This more modularised approach to construction can facilitate small-scale actors in completing their projects by reducing build times and the need for a large team of specialists onsite, with build quality and long-term energy costs being greatly improved. It leverages continuing technical innovation by introducing greater circularity into the build process, and improves customer engagement with community groups, social housing associations etc. getting a user experience that is in many ways more akin that experienced by larger corporations and business entities and is in contrast to the more atomised, disempowered consumer experience of individual property developers.

BM6: Community-based ESCO

By establishing a community-based ESCO, a group of stakeholders in a geographically defined area are able to come together to access a variety of financing options available to large-scale operatives, enabling them to leverage the funds needed to implement significant energy saving projects in their community; the retrofitting of older inefficient heating systems in existing housing stock in their area, for example. The subsequent savings in energy costs are, in turn, fed back in to servicing the loans required for the energy retrofit, monies that would traditionally only be available to largescale utilities or corporations. An Energy Services Company (ESCO) can be a commercial for-profit or a non-profit business that provides a range of energy services which can include any, all, or a combination of some of the following; design and implementation of energy projects for retrofitting or new-build, energy saving, energy monitoring, energy generation and energy supply.

Figure 10: BM6 Community based ESCO

Innovation: A key innovation of community-based ESCOs is in how local people can leverage novel financing arrangements that would be otherwise unattainable to them. Methods such as on-balance sheet debt financing, equity financing, mezzanine financing, off-balance sheet project financing, leasing, special purpose vehicles (SPV), and special purpose entity (SPE) make this possible and indicative of the types of technological and financing innovations discussed in *D2.3 Report on novel business models and main barriers in the EU energy system*. In this community-based ESCO BM there is no initial capital cost to the client – such costs can be a significant disincentive to many community groups – with financing and payment structures divided more equitably between the various partners. These costs may be covered by the ESCO, or a third-party financier, or indeed they may be shared between them with costs being recouped through the energy savings that are achieved. This BM would especially suit those spatially-dispersed communities that have traditionally either been ignored or marginalised during the roll-out of strategic infrastructure in the past.

BM7: An Internal or Virtual ESCO

Energy costs are a significant issue for large organisations too. An internal or virtual ESCO is another innovative BM that can be used by a large organisation operating under significant budgetary constraints, such as a hospital or university, but can still leverage the substantial annual expenditure required to run it. An internal ESCO, in this instance, would involve the organisation devising a split-incentive scheme whereby the individual departments that comprise it are given more control over their energy budgets with the proviso that they must incorporate energy saving strategies into their spending plans. This can vary from changing specific energy behaviours or work-based practices to retrofitting poorly-performing plant equipment. The substantial budgets involved, would enable the establishment of specific, goal-orientated public private partnerships (PPPs) where the private service provider installs the new plant equipment, in addition to holding the long-term maintain contracts with the hospital. Any financial savings made to the energy budgets of these departments can either be put back in to the overall budgets of the hospital, or be ring-fenced within the department to pay for the upgrading of other essential equipment or services. This would emerge from agreements made between the hospital and the individual departments.

Figure 11: BM7 An Internal or Virtual ESCO within a large organisation

Innovation: A key innovation of this type of ESCO again relates to financing tools involved, such as on-balance sheet debt financing, equity financing, mezzanine financing, off-balance sheet project financing, leasing, and special purpose vehicles (SPV). Internal ESCO business models therefore enable large organisation to introduce greater flexibility to what are usually quite rigid funding arrangements. By modularising the energy budgets down to the department level, large organisations can incentivise energy saving strategies that in turn contribute to any climate mitigation obligations they must adhere to while at the same time reduce costs.

BM8: Peer-to-Peer Community Energy Trading (P2P-CETs)

A group of investors establish a peer-to-peer energy trading entity, via an online trading platform that allows energy consumers buy electricity directly from independent producers, such as farmers with wind turbines on their properties. It acts as an energy supplier, linking consumers and generators, and balancing the market using modern information and communication technologies (ICT). The cloud-based technologies used in this business model also allow for dealing with local energy production excesses and can facilitate innovative recording and forecasting for device-specific electricity consumption. This additional service is designed to enable the energy trading entity to establish a virtual microgrid that customers can link into and avail of through the use of smart contracts. The facility will soon be made available whereby smaller scale producers, such as groups of building owners in a district can sell surplus energy generated from their installed solar PV panels directly to their neighbours using blockchain technology.

Figure 12: BM8 Peer-to-Peer Community Energy Trading (P2P-CETs)

Innovation: There are a number of innovative aspects to this type business model. In applying the classification of innovation categorisations set out in D2.3, it meets all three classifications in technological innovation contributing to optimization of energy system infrastructure, promotes circularity of supply and the substitution of traditional fossil fuels networks with more adaptable renewable energy configurations.

5.3 Shared Mobility

Car ownership and related consumption of space for car parking is one of the most urgent challenges shared by European cities and towns – and not really well treated in European and national transport policies. Congestion is another effect of having too many cars on limited street space. In fact, traffic congestion costs amount to 2% of GDP in cities such as Stuttgart and Paris, and on-street parking takes up 50% of inner-city land space (Ellen MacArthur Foundation, 2012). According to a study done on US cities, commuters can expect to spend more than 40 hours a year sitting in traffic by 2020 (Dovey Fishman, 2012).

However, whether because of convenience, safety, comfort, or choice of route and schedule, car travel is still the preferred mode of daily travel in some of the largest European cities, accounting for 45% in cities like Berlin or London (Rode, Hoffmann, Kandt, Smith, & Graff, 2015). Consequently, the challenge for urban planners today is to balance the demand for increasing personal mobility, with the need to respect the environment and provide an acceptable quality of life for all citizens. Experience has shown that adding new infrastructure is often expensive and slow. Therefore, urban planners and policy makers are interested in finding ways to make their existing infrastructure more efficient and encourage more use of alternative modes of transport.

Shared mobility schemes represent innovative responses to the demand for new options and offer an opportunity to reduce traffic congestion, to address last mile and first mile solutions and to identify choices for those who cannot afford to buy and maintain a vehicle, among others. Indeed, there is a variety of business models that share modes of transport among users. The range may go from car, bike and moto sharing, to carpooling or ride sharing (Paundra, Rook, van Dalen, & Ketter, 2017). It should be noted that although sharing vehicles is a growing trend, it is still a niche market today, estimated to represent just 1-4% of passenger kilometres globally (Bondorová & Archer, 2017). In fact, in the three core regions— Europe, China, and the United States—the shared-mobility market was nearly \$54 billion in 2016 (Grosse-Ophoff, Hausler, Heineke, & Möller, 2017), and it is expected to double by 2025 (Bondorová & Archer, 2017).

Amongst these services, the market for car sharing (which offers a car at your disposal without the need of ownership) has become one of the largest in Europe due to its potential to reduce the number of cars in cities without reducing individual mobility (Perboli, Ferrero, Musso, & Vesco, 2017). In the city of Bremen, for example, each shared car proved to be the equivalent of taking 15 private cars off the road (Glotz-Richter, 2016). Similarly, each shared car in France proved to liberate four parking places, according to a study carried out by 6t in partnership with ADEME¹⁴.

Car sharing first made its debut in Europe in the 1980s in Switzerland, and in 1990 in Bremen and other German cities, long before the digital age and the sharing economy ever emerged. In fact, most organizations

¹⁴ French Environment and Energy Management Agency

started out in environmentally concerned local communities that wanted to meet their mobility needs in a more sustainable way (Loose, 2014). These early organizations were arranged in a Business-to-Consumer (B2C) form, in which the organization (operating for-profit or not-for-profit) owns a fleet of cars that the customers can use. At first, the general operational characteristics of these organisations were similar to the round-trip business model, where cars are picked up and returned to the same parking spot from which they departed.

While the popularity of car sharing was local and never took off, it is a different story today, where growing urbanisation—particularly by younger people who are less dependent on car ownership—is changing mobility patterns and desires. In fact, car sharing is most effective and attractive when seen as a transportation mode that fills the gap between transit and private cars and can be linked to other modes and transportation services as a mobility package. Cities, as hotbeds of connectivity and innovation, can provide the right market conditions for shared vehicles to shift towards modal integration.

According to (Sanvicente, Kielmanowicz, Rodenbach, Chicco, & Ramos, n.d.), in a study carried out in the framework of the European project STARS¹⁵, there are three types of underlying forces that are essential to understanding the new era of mobility and particularly the future of car sharing.

First, the arrival of digital technologies, starting with the development of the Internet, to social media platforms and subsequently widespread of smartphones. Indeed, smart technologies have made choosing, booking and using shared transport easier, while access to cars was eased through smart cards and later smart locks. While automatic car sharing systems already started in 90's with the installation of the first on-board computer and GPS standards (Shaheen, Sperling, & Wagner, 1999), Internet of Things (IoT) holds a great promise enhancing fleet maintenance. Indeed, functionalities such as real-time journey planning and parking place availability check (Albertson, 2017) will improve the shared mobility experience of users. On a longer term, blockchain is pointed out to shape peer-to-peer car sharing, potentially changing the roles of intermediaries, facilitating financial transactions and developing transparent usage-based insurances. Finally, big data analytics will help car sharing operators enhance fleet management, by analysing, for example, information on the idle times of vehicles for particular areas in the city (OECD, 2016).

Second, automotive advances. Beyond digitisation, innovations related to urban transport focuses on further electrification of urban mobility systems. Indeed, several European cities are already combining these strategies with car sharing services. The largest EV car sharing scheme is the Autolib programme in Paris, with 3,923 vehicles and 1,086 stations (*Rapport d'activite 2016*, 2016). The arrival of driverless autonomous vehicles (AVs), on the other hand, represents a unique opportunity for fundamental change in urban mobility. However, a path based mainly on individual ownership of autonomous cars would not exploit the potential

¹⁵ The STARS project stands for “*Shared mobility opporTunities And challenges foR European citieS*” and it received funding from the H2020 Programme under grant agreement n°769513: <http://stars-h2020.eu/>

of autonomous vehicles for sustainable transport but could lead to an increase of vehicle mileage without reducing car ownership and related space consumption. Such a scenario could serve to reduce already-low average vehicle occupancy to less than one as vehicles move around the city with no occupants. Indeed, it should be noted that according to UITP's latest policy brief on the topic (UITP, 2017), AVs will only help to reduce the number of cars (reduce car ownership, car traffic and parking needs) and drastically improve mobility options, if they come as shared fleets integrated with public transport.

Third, sharing economy practices that, emerging from 2008, are growing into a cultural consumption approach. Whether classified under the label of rental economy, peer-to-peer or on-demand, these new forms of sharing economy practices are the result of the interlinking of four types main driving forces, including technology enablers (mobile devices), connectivity, environmental concerns, and global recession.

Looking at the challenges European cities face, it is clear that Europe needs to acknowledge the potential of car sharing in its policy papers and recommendations for urban mobility measures. This includes, not only looking at both ICT based and innovations and the inclusion of autonomous transport systems, their impacts on the urban mobility environment and the related infrastructure needed, but also societal changes taking place nowadays.

According to Tart, Wells, Beccaria, & Sanvicente (n.d.) today's car sharing organisations can be classified into five main types of business models, based upon their operational characteristics and business model variables: 1) free-floating with an operational area; 2) free-floating with pool stations; 3) roundtrip, home-zone based; 4) roundtrip, station-based; and 5) Peer-to-peer (P2P). As will be discussed in the following, each type of business model has its own distinct characteristics, partner tendencies, and pricing habits, regardless of whether it is for-profit or not-for-profit. It should be noted that there is no one business model that is better than the others. The model that fits a rural area will not be the same one that fits a dense urban area. Likewise, the choice of consumers often depends upon personal preferences. The same goes for local authorities, who may have a preference for one type over the other, depending upon the policy outcomes they want to achieve.

BM9: Free-floating Car Sharing with an Operational Area (FCSOA)

A car rental company sets up a FCSOA business model focusing on urban areas and college campuses across Europe and North America, offering a selection of cars option that serve multiple purposes, including hauling office supplies and private property from different rental accommodation. Working with several partners it has been able to boosting its value proposition. For example, it works with local authorities to secure free parking on public streets for its members; and with city councils setting up charging bays for the EV segment of its fleet. It also provides its members with discounts to local businesses that it partners with and it integrates its network with local public transport. Depending on the package chosen members pay a monthly subscription charge and their trip charges are calculated based on the length of time they use the car. A deposit is not required. In this business model, members choose a car nearby and then return it by leaving it in any valid parking spot within a defined district. This is the most flexible of all business models, providing drivers with the freedom to make one-way trips, in addition to offering them a variety of parking options.

Figure 13: BM9 Free-floating Car Sharing with an Operational Area

Innovation: There are a number of innovative aspects to this type business model. Applying the classification of innovation categories set out in D2.3, it meets all four classifications in experience innovation contributing to greater PSS-Functionality, better Customer Engagement while Channelling innovations between customer offerings and existing infrastructure and offering novel integrated product system services to its customers. According to a recent study carried out in the United States (Rubicon, 2015), the use of this type of BM has resulted in the removal between 9 to 13 private cars off the road for every shared car deployed. It has also resulted in a reduction of vehicle miles travelled (VMT) of between 1% and 5% depending on the location, with the greatest reduction in urban areas (Stocker, Lazarus, Becker, & Shaheen, 2016).

BM10: Free-floating Car Sharing with Pool Stations (FCSPS)

A car sharing service is established to offer a wide-ranging, public, electric car sharing service at the municipal level, which acts as an extension of the public transport services. Its customer based is aimed at both the more environmentally aware and urban drivers who simply need a (compact) car to get around the city. The free-floating with pool station model allows members to make one-way trips and then park the car at a number of charging stations situated at ideal locations around the city. The company offers its members a service that is complementary to public transport, as many of the stations are located close to metro stations and/or bus stops. Users have the option of adding this type of car sharing account to their existing public transport card, making multi-modal transport easier. Charging stations are often strategically placed near metro stations or in key commercial and residential districts. For members who buy an annual pass, they have the opportunity to earn points and access to a range of benefits and special offers, with drivers paying based on the time they use the vehicle for (per minute of use, once they have gone over the initial allocated time of 20 minutes). They also have the choice of paying a monthly fee, or a reservation fee each time they use the service.

Figure 14: BM10 Free-floating Car Sharing with Pool Stations

Innovation: This type of BM is still quite rare and relies exclusively on large EV fleets and requires more than just subscription fees and rental usage fees to be financially profitable. As a result, organisations may have to diversify their revenue streams such as selling advertising space on both the inside and outside of their cars. A notable innovation of this type of business model is the exclusive reliance on electric vehicles, without the back up of any other fuel-type vehicle. This places it firmly in the substitution with renewables technological innovation, in addition to the experience innovations discussed in BM9.

BM11: Roundtrip, Home-zone Car Sharing (RHCS)

The roundtrip, home-zone based BM offers a service whereby drivers are incentivised to return the car to the general area from which they started. It might be helpful to think of it as a neighbourhood business model, where the vehicles are often located in residential areas, for the nearly exclusive use of local residents. While the roundtrip aspect means that drivers do not have the flexibility to take one-way trips, the area/zone-based aspect means that cars can be parked in any valid spot, as long as it is within the same zone or neighbourhood of its departure, providing users with a degree of flexibility in terms parking. Customers attracted to this BM include car enthusiasts wanting to try new models, and those who are open to new forms of mobility. While members do not have access to free city parking, they can avail of discounted parking rates. Its value proposition also offers members the opportunity to drive new cars with keyless entry, members able to upload photographs of the cars they drove as proof of condition, once they have returned it. Also, another online aspect to this model involves members blogging about their car sharing experiences, for which they get credits that they can use against their next rental. Members pay monthly fees in addition to usage fees based on the kilometre driven and the hours used.

Figure 15: Roundtrip, Home-zone Car Sharing

Innovation: A rather unique aspect of this business model is the partnership established between the company operating the RHCS BM, the leasing company supplying the cars and car manufacturer. This allows for a more integrated approach to maintenance and supply. Like the other BMs in this section a notable innovation is to the profit model referred to in D2.3. with companies finding new ways to convert their assets in valuable revenue streams, while also offering established companies, including car manufacturers and leasing companies, a glimpse of where future mobility might be headed. Incentivising driver usage rates through improved usability at reasonable rates demonstrate how to collect new revenue streams can be created from existing structures.

BM12: Peer-to-Peer Car Sharing (P2P-CS)

The P2P-CS BM operates much like roundtrip car sharing BMs. However, this BM leverages the user’s own car, which is rented out, rather than hosting its own fleet of vehicles. This enables a car owner to make money by renting it out when it would otherwise be sitting idle. When drivers are finished with the car, they return it to the car owner’s home or home-zone area. Where they return it to will often depend on the size of the city in which the P2P organisation operates, as many car owners in larger cities may not have private parking spaces, and drivers will therefore park it on public streets nearby (essentially making it area/zone-based). The value proposition, customer segments, and other key features of P2P organisations result in a very different business model from those of the roundtrip organisations. Likewise, as each car owner brings his or her own car—and personality—to the group, one organisation’s application of the business model may differ greatly from another. The service offered by organisation using the P2P-CS BM enables its users to rent other people’s cars within walking distance of their home whenever they need one: whether it is to attend a business meeting, go around the city, go away for a weekend, or move to a new house. Unlike its counterparts this BM does not need to capture drivers who need to take short trips inside a city, but rather focuses instead on keeping repeat customers, and drivers who are in need of a car for longer trips.

Figure 16: Peer-to-Peer Car Sharing

Innovation: One value proposition of note for this type of BM is that new members are offered training on how to get started. Car owners are allowed to rent their car to other members, setting their own price. A GPS unit is installed in the car, to prevent against theft and car owners keep 70% of the rental amount. There is no subscription fee, and a deposit is not required. At the end of their trip, drivers can leave reviews of their experience, helping to ensure members are honest and fair. A notable innovation in this BM is the flexibility associated with customer engagement and PSS-Functionality.

6 Conclusion

A key goal of the ENTRUST has been to gain an in-depth understanding of how human behaviour around energy is shaped by both technological systems and socio- demographic factors. As part of this goal the project provides a mapping of the energy system in Europe and explores how new approaches to public policy, business innovation and community engagement can contribute to meeting the potentials offered by the energy transition. While, granted, we can accept that socio-technical transitions are complex multi-level long-term transitional processes, which can radically alter existing relatively stable socio-technological regimes, there is now also broad agreement that there is a very clear need to drive societal development towards energy configurations that offer increased socioeconomic sustainability and that do not further endanger the environmental systems we depend on for survival.

The primary aim of WP6 has been to develop novel and effective means through which situated, practice-based understandings of new energy technologies, behaviour and integrated socio-technical interventions can be best used to support a transition to a low carbon energy system. The means through which new technologies and energy system stakeholders can be engaged and activated to shape and progressively interact with the energy system in ways to actively deliver a low carbon paradigm have been outlined progressively through each deliverable associated with this WP. D6.4 Innovative Business Models to Foster Transition is the final research deliverable of this WP. Its principle goal has been to present a discussion of business models that have the potential to contribute meaningfully to the energy transition. Building on earlier deliverables, most notably D2.3 Report on novel business models and main barriers in the EU energy system, D5.3 Energy Management Approaches for Sustainable Communities and earlier deliverables D6.1, D6.2 and D6.3 of this work packages this deliverable has sought to both outline the processes that shape our understanding of how business models can be applied to foster change. Each of the 12 business models outlined in this deliverable offer the degree of flexibility and adaptability required for operating within current transitioning frameworks and therefore can be used independently or in combination with other models.

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